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Pathways to Inclusion: Towards truly inclusive labour markets

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PATHS2INCLUDE

PATHS 2 INCLUDE

European Labour Markets Under Pressure –
New knowledge on pathways to include persons
in vulnerable situations

Title: Pathways to Inclusion: Towards truly inclusive labour markets

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Contents

Introduction: what we mean by inclusive labour markets and why they matter	4
2. Factors of labour market vulnerability observed in PATHS2INCLUDE research findings	5
2.1. Difference between inactivity and unemployment	5
2.2. The individual level.....	5
2.3. The interaction with the broader context.....	6
3. Policy recommendations: how can we reach more inclusive labour markets?	8
Pillar 1 – Remove structural barriers to participation.....	8
Pillar 2 – Create inclusive regional labour markets.....	9
References.....	11

Introduction: what we mean by inclusive labour markets and why they matter

Ensuring equal access to the labour market for persons in vulnerable situations remains a major challenge across Europe. Although the inclusiveness of European labour markets has been improving over the last decades, numerous social groups, such as women, migrants, persons with disabilities, and older workers, continue to face disadvantages in the labour market (OECD, 2020).

Evidence from the PATHS2INCLUDE project shows that labour market exclusion does not depend only on individual characteristics, but also on the interplay between personal and contextual factors throughout the life course.

The specific combination of intersecting characteristics, and how they shape labour market outcomes, may vary across different contexts and regional labour markets (Fernandez et al., 2016; Sundaram et al., 2014). Labour market vulnerability is intended here as the interaction between individual disadvantages and structural conditions such as welfare regimes, labour market regulations, and prevailing social norms (e.g., Esping-Andersen, 1990; Lewis, 1992; Pfau-Effinger, 2004).

From a capability and human rights-based perspective, Nussbaum (2011) identifies decent work as a basic human need. Defined by fair employment conditions and adequate income, it supports a range of other capabilities, including maintaining good health, developing meaningful social relationships, avoiding exploitation, gaining respect, participating in decision-making, fostering self-esteem and agency, and enjoying adequate leisure time. Conversely, lack of access to decent work (Abbot et al., 2016) can generate structural disadvantages and perpetuate cycles of social exclusion. Employment participation gaps, whether rooted in gender, disability, or other factors, erode quality of life and limit the scope of individual opportunities.

Inclusive labour markets are not only a moral imperative, but they are also key to productivity, innovation, and long-term growth. By tapping into the full potential of all workers, Europe strengthens both its competitiveness and social cohesion. Inclusive labour markets, which are able to increase wellbeing not only for the average person but also for groups in vulnerable situations, represent a competitive advantage in terms of the European social model compared to other world economies. In this sense, more inclusive labour markets, understood as accelerators of rights and participation, are a way to keep cohesion strong on the home front at a time of particular turbulence and growing detachment from pro-European sentiments. By ensuring that all individuals can access fair employment opportunities, we not only reduce inequalities but also strengthen the sense of belonging within the European Union.

2. Factors of labour market vulnerability observed in PATHS2INCLUDE research findings

2.1. Difference between inactivity and unemployment

A key insight is the difference between inactivity (being unavailable for work) and unemployment (looking for job but not being able to find one). These are shaped by partly distinct factors and therefore require tailored policies. The economically inactive may be excluded for diverse reasons, including inability to work (e.g., due to health barriers, care obligations etc.), formal/informal rules, the discouraged-worker effect (Benati, 2001), or adaptive preferences (Teschi & Comim, 2005). For many, “having/finding a job” lies outside what is realistically achievable. Unemployment is a different deprivation: unemployed people see themselves as workers unable to find suitable work matching their needs, expectations, and skills. This distinction suggests that to reach, on the contrary, activation and employment, even though they are two interlinked concepts, they are also shaped by partly distinct factors and merit separate investigation.

- **Younger workers** tend to be the most active, but also the least likely to find a job when they look for one.
- **Women** are less likely to be active in the labour market compared to men but show no significant difference in employment once active. This suggests that while women may face barriers to participation, once these are overcome, they have similar employment prospects.
- **Single parents**, compared to other forms of households, show higher activation but significantly lower employment probabilities, likely due to caregiving constraints, sectoral segregation, and more. This highlights the need for targeted measures to support single parents, who are willing to work but face structural barriers to employment.

2.2. The individual level

Our analysis of data from the 27 EU countries and Norway (2010–2022) shows that several individual characteristics strongly shape labour market opportunities (Vivoli et al., 2024):

- **Health-related limitations** (often a proxy for disability) are among the main drivers of exclusion. Individuals with poor health are more likely to be inactive and unemployed, and face greater risks of job insecurity, especially during economic crises.

- **Older workers** are exposed to specific risks, amplified during the COVID-19 pandemic, and age interacts with several other dimensions. Poor health is a key factor pushing older workers into involuntary exit from the labour market. Gender dynamics also matter: older women with partners are more likely to retire voluntarily, reflecting persistent stereotypical household roles. Lower-educated workers are at higher risk of both voluntary and involuntary exit, due to lower adaptability to technological change and higher replaceability.
- **Care responsibilities** significantly reduce labour market attachment, particularly for women.
- **Education** is the strongest protection against exclusion. Higher education and digital skills increased resilience during the shift to remote work, while low-skilled workers faced greater difficulties.
- **Wealth** moderates risks: the negative impact of poor health on labour market participation is much lower among wealthier individuals. Similarly, women in higher wealth quintiles face substantially lower risks of exclusion.

2.3. The interaction with the broader context

Beyond individual characteristics, context strongly shapes labour market opportunities:

- **Regional labour market conditions matter.** Individuals in regions with higher economic activity and lower unemployment are more likely to be active and employed, regardless of their individual characteristics.
- **Physical infrastructure plays a crucial role in shaping labour market outcomes.** The availability of transport networks (proxied by km of motorway network/1000 km²) has a measurable impact both on labour market activation and on actual employment.
- **Economic diversification** strengthens resilience to shocks: regions with multiple thriving sectors show better employment outcomes.
- **Human capital endowment** (measured through regional tertiary education levels) supports activation, though strong competition among highly educated workers can reduce employment opportunities.
- **Active Labour Market Policies (ALMPs)** are effective: regions with stronger ALMPs report higher activity and employment rates.

Vulnerabilities do not play out uniformly, they are shaped by the wealth of the region:

- **Regional wealth gaps amplify inequalities.** For example, a male older worker with average characteristics in a low-GDP region has less than half the chance of being employed if active compared to one in a high-GDP region (12% vs 27%).

For 15–24-year-old women with average characteristics, the gap is similar (22% vs 31%).

Figure 1: Estimated probabilities of employment by gender, age and region.

Source: Authors' elaboration with EU-SILC data

- Even in wealthier regions, **risks remain high for individuals with specific vulnerabilities**. For instance, women aged 25–54 in high-GDP regions have a 39% chance of employment if active, but this drops to 30% with a chronic illness, and to just 9% with significant care responsibilities.

Figure 2: Estimated probabilities of employment for women with specific vulnerabilities

Source: Authors' elaboration with EU-SILC data

- **Paradox of activation without employment:** people with health limitations are more likely to be active in wealthier regions, due to stronger demand, but not necessarily employed. They often end up in less protected sectors, which increases their risk of unemployment.

3. Policy recommendations: how can we reach more inclusive labour markets?

To enhance labour market inclusion, this section proposes policy recommendations based on PATHS2INCLUDE research findings and the outcomes of the Policy Round Table on the role of EU policy in shaping inclusive labour markets which was organised in context of the project.¹ The recommendations are structured into two pillars:

Pillar 1 – Remove structural barriers to participation

- **Support work-life balance and caregiving:** expand affordable, accessible childcare and eldercare services, alongside flexible work arrangements such as remote work, part-time schemes with career progression, or carers' leave that does not penalise employment prospects. These measures are particularly critical for women and single parents, who face higher risks of involuntary exit due to unmet care demands. At the same time, it should be recognised that flexible work arrangements are not a suitable solution for everyone, as they require a solid set of digital skills. This highlights the parallel need for targeted investments in skills development, ensuring that all workers can benefit from new forms of work organisation.
- **Enhance workplace accommodations for older and disabled workers:** promote clear and cost-effective procedures for employers to adapt workplaces (e.g., ergonomic adjustments, assistive technologies, flexible scheduling). Such measures should be supported by public guidelines and funding mechanisms, making inclusive employment both feasible and sustainable for employers. These measures should be inspired also by recommendations contained in the Review of the EU by the UNCRPD committee published in March 2025 (UNCRPD, 2025).
- **Reform paternity leave policies to extend the length and eligibility,** as research indicates that these reforms can contribute to shifting gender norms and increasing male participation in household responsibilities (Farré et al. 2023).

¹ Read more about the Policy Round table: <https://paths2include.eu/project-updates/policy-round-table-on-the-role-of-eu-policy-in-shaping-inclusive-labour-markets-key-outcomes/>

- **Strengthen the enforcement of equal pay and anti-discrimination laws** to promote fair labour practices. Encourage companies to adopt proactive policies, such as pay audits, diversity strategies, and transparency obligations, to demonstrate progress in closing gender gaps and building inclusive workplaces. Also, strengthen the role of equality bodies and intersectional monitoring: ensure that national equality bodies are fully equipped, both legally and financially, to monitor the application of EU anti-discrimination legislation in the labour market. On this, the European Commission should provide clearer guidelines on applying an intersectional perspective, enabling equality bodies to capture how multiple disadvantages (e.g., gender, age, disability, care, migrant status) interact in shaping labour outcomes. Good practices, such as Belgium’s use of a “diversity barometer” to study age discrimination across sectors, should be promoted and adopted in other Member States.²

Pillar 2 – Create inclusive regional labour markets

- **Promote economic diversification:** support regional development strategies that invest in multiple thriving sectors, especially in areas highly dependent on a single industry. Diversified economies are more resilient to shocks, create varied employment opportunities, and reduce the vulnerability of workers to sector-specific downturns. EU and national funds should be mobilised to foster innovation, support the green and digital transition, and sustainable industries at the local level.
- **Enhance mobility and territorial connectivity through public transport and housing policies:** while flexible work arrangements can benefit some groups, they are not suitable for all, particularly in sectors that require physical presence in the workplace. To ensure equal access to employment opportunities, governments and regions should invest in reliable, affordable, accessible and fast public transport systems that connect workers with job locations and to childcare services across territories, as well as in equitable housing policies. Improving mobility reduces geographical barriers to employment, supports participation in both urban and rural labour markets, and prevents workers in vulnerable situations from being excluded due to limited ability to commute to work.

² The Diversity Barometer on Education, Employment and Housing for Belgium can be found here: <https://www.unia.be/en/knowledge-recommendations/diversity-barometer-education-2018?lang=en>

- **Strengthen Active Labour Market Policies (ALMPs):** scale up well-designed programmes that combine training, career counselling, wage subsidies, and targeted job placement services for people in vulnerable situations.
- **Address the activation–employment gap:** recognise that being “active” in the labour market does not automatically translate into employment. Tailored interventions to the different realities of unemployed people (who seek but cannot find work) and inactive people (who may face health barriers, care obligations, or discouragement). Policies should support transitions into actual employment by providing job-matching services, tackling discrimination in hiring, and offering subsidised employment pathways—with target measures particularly for youth, women, and single parents.

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